

AN IMPROVED METHOD FOR JOINING COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this investigation, an improved design for adhesive composite single lap joints was proposed. The addition of attachments on both sides of the lapped region of single lap joint proved to be more efficient in terms of load transfer. This design concept achieved compressive normal stresses at the ends of the lapped region in place of singular peel stresses in the single lap joint. The new joint has achieved about 59 % improvement in tensile shear. The effect of the adherend lay-up on the ultimate strength, especially the ply next to the adhesive layer was investigated. The stiffness of the attachment achieved by changing the lay-up without increasing the thickness was shown to have no effect on the ultimate loads.

KEYWORDS: Single lap joint, film adhesive, composites, attachment, interface, crack.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesively bonded joints have increasingly been used in many applications in aerospace, marine, and automotive industries. Since many joints encountered in these industries are made of advanced composite materials, the importance of improving the performance of these joints is highly desirable.

There are major joint designs for in-plane load transfers through the use of mechanical fasteners and adhesive bonding. From the literature, it is observed that the mechanical fastening can achieve only a maximum tensile strength of 50 % of the weakest adherend in the joint due to the stress concentrations caused by the fastener holes, whereas adhesively bonded joints can achieve about 80 % of the tensile strength of the weakest adherend [1]. This has contributed to the increasing use of adhesive joining in aerospace, marine and automotive industries.

Structural adhesives have poor resistance to normal (peel) stresses, but are adequate in shear and strong in compression. Ideally, an efficient joint design should avoid the presence of tensile peel stress along the bondline. Of all lap joint designs, the single-lap joint is generally the simplest and least expensive to manufacture. However, its intrinsic load eccentricity and highly localized interfacial stresses at the ends of the lapped region make it inefficient in load transfer [2,3]. Failure often occurs at the ends of the joint due to the singular tensile normal stresses. A considerable amount of work has been done on the single lap joint in the last few decades [4-6]. To improve the joint strength, some have suggested altering the adherend geometry to reduce the peak interfacial stresses [7,8]. Sawyer [9], and Tong et al [10] showed that significant improvements in static strength can be obtained by transverse stitching of adhesively bonded composite joints. Mazumdar and Mallick [11] experimentally investigated the effects of recessing (a concept in which the adhesive layer is placed at regular intervals, instead of as a continuous layer) on the failure load of single lap joints. They showed that the average strength of the bond increases with recessing. Zeng and Sun [12] designed a wavy configuration in the joint region to achieve a compressive peel stress in a single lap joint with the result of significantly increasing both the static and fatigue strengths. Cameron et al [13] showed that, by increasing the number of planes that transfer load, the strength can be increased. Analytical modeling and finite element analyses have been performed to analyze the stress/strain distributions in the adhesive and the adherends [14,15]. Quasi-static failure mechanism and strength have been investigated

[16,17]. Methods have been developed and used in the designs of single and double lap joints, step lap joint, and scarf joint [18].

Recently, Turaga and Sun [19] proposed a new design concept involving the use of attachments for aluminum single lap joints. In the present investigation, the design of adding thin structural attachments to the joint region is investigated. The function of the attachment is to add additional load transfer locations and load paths and, thus, minimize the level of interfacial stresses. It turns out that the attachment, in fact, makes the interfacial stresses along the original bondline compressive.

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF THE JOINT

The new joint design is shown in Fig. 1 which is basically a conventional single lap joint with two additional attachments. S2/8552 glass/epoxy composite material was used to make the adherends and attachments. Flat $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$ laminates were cured in an autoclave first and then cut into adherends of width 25.4 mm. The attachments were of $[0]_{12}$ lay-up. A specially made aluminum mold shown in Fig. 2 was used to make the attachments. An angle of 30° was manufactured for the bent portion of the attachment (see Fig. 1). The angle of the attachment is the angle made by the inclined portion of the attachment against the adherend. The attachment has a curvature at the bent portion. In the finite element modeling, the shape of the attachment was that measured from the mold. The selected joint dimensions are shown in Fig. 1. The thickness of the adherend is about 2.6 mm with 32 plies of S2 /epoxy laminae. The attachment thickness is 0.9 mm.

Fig. 1 Geometry and dimensions of the single lap joint with attachment

Fig. 2 Aluminum mold for manufacturing the composite attachment

Surface Preparation

Before curing the joints in the autoclave, proper surface preparations of the adherend and attachment need to be done. The importance of surface pretreatment in the adhesive bonding of composite materials has been well established by a number of researchers [20,21]. Surface treatment of composites is to remove contamination layers.

In the present investigation, basic steps as follows were applied.

Peel ply surface: While manufacturing the composite laminate, a peel ply was used which gives a rough surface that is required for bonding. The use of this peel ply avoids the need to perform sanding with 320 grit sandpaper.

MEK /Acetone treatment: The surfaces to be bonded are treated with Methyl Ethyl Ketone or Acetone solution to remove the greasy substances formed while handling and other contaminants formed on the composite surface during curing.

Distilled water treatment: The degreased surfaces were then cleaned with distilled water and the water-break-free test as described in the previous chapter was performed.

Drying: The composite adherends and attachments to be bonded were kept in oven at about 100° C for 1-2 hrs to remove any moisture present on the surface. Removing moisture is very important as the presence of moisture was observed to cause poor bonding and thereby result in cohesive failure, i. e., failure between the adherend and adhesive.

A single layer of structural film adhesive FM73M was used to bond the joints in the autoclave under the pressure of 280Kpa, producing an average bondline thickness of around 0.127 mm along the five interfaces. Ready-to-be-tested single lap joint with attachments is shown in Fig. 3. The structural film adhesive FM73M was used to bond the specimens in the autoclave using the standard cure cycle for FM73M.

Fig. 3 Composite single lap joint with attachment

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Tension tests were conducted using a servo-hydraulic testing machine (20 kips MTS testing machine) at room temperature. All the joints were tested at a stroke speed of 0.001 mm/sec till failure. Two to four specimens were tested for each type of design. The onset of failure during experiment was monitored and failure modes were noted for all the specimens. It was observed that the conventional single lap joint specimens failed at an average load of 21.4 kN while the single lap joints with attachments failed at an average load of 34 kN, thereby giving an increase of 59 % in strength. The ultimate loads are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Ultimate loads of composite single lap joints with and without attachments

Joint type	Ultimate loads, kN	Average load
Single lap joint	21.4, 21.6, 20.9, 21.4	21.4
Single lap with attachments	34.5, 33.4	34
Increase in Strength		59%

The load-displacement curves for both joints are shown in Fig. 4. For the single lap joint, failure started at both the edges of the joint, and the joint failed suddenly. For the joint with attachments, the initial failure started in the form of a disbond crack at the critical interface (see Fig. 1) near the bend of the attachment. The average length of this initial crack formed before the joint failure was 11 mm, with no significant growth beyond the. The initial failure started at around 26.5-28 kN which can be noted as a small load drop in Fig. 4. After the initial failure, the joint took more loads before failing at about 34 kN. Using a traveling microscope, it was observed that the final failure was the failure of the main interface. The failure mode just before the final catastrophic failure is shown in Fig. 5. The crack at the leading edge of the main interface (see Fig. 1) can be clearly seen.

Fig. 4 Load displacement curves for the composite lap joint with and without attachment.

Fig. 5 Failure mode of the composite lap joint with attachment
FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Finite element analyses with 2-D plane strain quadrilateral elements were performed for composite single lap joints with and without attachments to compare the interfacial stress distributions. Very fine meshes were used near the places where stress singularities exist. In the adhesive layer, 8 elements across the thickness were used. The elastic constants of FM73M film adhesive and S2 glass/epoxy composite are shown in Table 2. For simplicity, the adherend and attachment laminates were represented by homogeneous solids whose effective elastic moduli were calculated following Sun and Li [22]. Since the FM73M film adhesive is highly nonlinear as shown in Fig. 6, it was modeled as an elastic-plastic material obeying the von Mises yield criterion and the associated flow rule. The curve in Fig. 6 was derived from the shear stress-strain curve obtained by the manufacturer using a lap shear test of the adhesive.

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-strain curve for FM73M

Table 2 Material properties of S2/8552 and FM73M

Material	Properties
FM73M	E=2.3 GPa; $\nu=0.31$
S2 glass/epoxy	$E_1=50$ GPa, $E_2=20$ GPa, $E_3=20$ GPa; $\nu_{12}=0.27$, $\nu_{23}=0.4$, $\nu_{13}=0.27$; $G_{12}=7$ GPa, $G_{23}=3.5$ GPa, $G_{13}=7$ GPa

The normal and shear stresses, σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} , along the main interface at the mid-plane of the adhesive under an applied tensile load of 21.4 kN for both single lap joints with/without attachments are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that the addition of attachments has the effect of making the normal stress compressive and reducing the shear stress. The stress distributions along the critical interface, i.e. the interface of the attachment and the adherend are presented in Fig. 8 along with the stress distributions along the main interface in the conventional single lap joint.

Fig. 7 Comparison of interfacial stress distributions along the main interfaces for single lap joints with and without attachments

Fig. 8 Comparison of stress distributions along the critical and main interfaces of single lap joints with and without attachments

As seen from the experimental results, the addition of attachments shifts the failure location from the main interface to the interface (denoted as critical interface in Fig. 1) between the attachment and adherend. Along this critical interface, the initial failure in all the specimens occurred at the bend region of the attachment. As can be seen from the stress distributions in Fig. 8, the end of this interface region is most critical and hence the initial failure is expected to initiate from this region. The initial failure forms a crack of a maximum length around 11 mm along the critical interface before the joint suffered the final failure.

PARAMETRIC STUDY

Effect of the ply orientation next to the adhesive layer

In the above experiments, the stacking sequence used for the adherends was $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$ and for the attachments was $[0]_{12}$. Here the ply next to the adhesive layer was a 0° ply. Since this ply may have an effect on the failure modes of the joints, the effect of changing this ply to a 90° ply was investigated.

Experiments were conducted using. From the results listed in Table 3 we can observe that placing a 90° ply next to the adhesive layer is not beneficial to the joint strength. The failure load of the single lap joint without attachments was 16.8 kN which is 21 % less than the load of 21.4kN for the $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$ adherends. For the single lap joint with attachments, the average failure load dropped by 27% with the use of $[90/0/90/0]_{4s}$ adherends. The reason for the reduction in joint strength with the $[90/0/90/0]_{4s}$ adherends is that failure occurs in the 90° ply in the adherend as opposed to the cohesive failure of the joints with the $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$ adherend. A typical failure surface in a single lap joint with $[90/0/90/0]_{4s}$ adherends is shown in Fig. 9 in which the transverse matrix cracks in the 90° ply are visible.

In view of the foregoing, it can be concluded that a 90° ply in the adherend next to the adhesive layer can alter the failure mode and lower the joint strength and, hence, is not recommended. Nevertheless, it still demonstrates that the design concept of attachment works equally well for the adherends having 90° plies on the surface.

Table 3 Effect of 90° ply next to the adhesive layer

Joint Type	Average ultimate load, kN for $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$	Average ultimate load, kN for $[90/0/90/0]_{4s}$
Single lap joint	21.4	16.8
Single lap with attachment	34	24.7
% difference	59	47

Fig. 9 Failure mode of the joint with $[90/0/90/0]_{4s}$ adherends

Effect of attachment stiffness

A composite joint offers more parameters for an efficient joint design like studying the effect of stiffness of the attachment by changing the number of 0° plies in the attachment, which are the primary load carrying members of the composite. Hence a parametric study to investigate the effect of the stiffness of the attachment, by changing the number of 0° layers instead of changing the thickness of the attachment was conducted both experimentally and numerically.

Two attachments, a stiffer $[0]_{12}$ laminate and a softer $[0/90/0]_{2s}$ laminate, were used for the joints with adherends made of $[0/90/0/90]_{4s}$ laminate. The ultimate failure loads for both types of joints are presented in Table 4. A total of four joints were tested for each type. It appears that there is no significant difference in the failure loads. It was observed that the failure modes of the joints were also the same, with the failure initiating from the critical interface near the bend region for both types of joints. The final failure occurred catastrophically in the form of cracking in the main interface following the initial failure.

Table 4 Effect of the stiffness of attachment

Specimen type	$[0]_{12}$ attachment	$[0/90_2/0/90_2]_s$ attachment
Ultimate loads, kN	33.4, 34.5	35.9, 34
Average	34	34.9

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that the new design of the single lap joint with composite adherends and attachments can significantly increase the strength over the joint without attachments. Failure modes of the new joint with attachments as well as the conventional single lap joint are affected by the ply next to the adhesive layer. Placing a 0° ply in the adherend next to the adhesive layer is beneficial to the joint strength whereas a 90° ply would crack before the adhesive fails. For the configuration of the attachment considered in this study, it can be concluded that the critical location for initial failure in the new joint design is at the end of the interface between the adherend and the attachment near the bend of the attachment. Increasing the stiffness of the attachment by increasing number of 0° plies without changing the thickness does not seem to be able to alleviate the interfacial stress at this critical location and, thus, does not have noticeable effects on the joint strength.

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